

THE ROLE OF DELAMINATION IN NOTCHED AND UNNOTCHED TENSILE STRENGTH

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SUMMARY

Delamination is usually associated with through-thickness failure, but in fact can have a major effect on in-plane strength of notched and unnotched laminates. This paper considers tensile strength of quasi-isotropic laminates and results from scaled tests to show how delamination is critical in damage development and ultimate failure.

Keywords: Delamination, Tensile strength, Notches, Hole size effect, Scaling

INTRODUCTION

Delamination is widely recognised as the Achilles heel of composite structures. A lot of effort has gone into researching delamination due to through-thickness stresses arising at features such as ply drops and free edges [e.g. 1, 2]. However, it is less widely appreciated that delamination also has a crucial role in determining in-plane strength, often leading to premature initiation of failure. Failure of composites is driven by the energy released as they are unloaded. This can occur in two ways: by fibre failure, or by delamination and matrix cracks joining up to produce a fracture surface without the need to break fibres. The latter mechanism is illustrated in Fig. 1 which shows schematically a (45/-45)_s laminate that has failed in tension by pull-out without any fibre failure. Similar phenomena can also affect failure in other layups. In this paper the role of delamination in unnotched and notched tensile strength of quasi-isotropic laminates is considered, and it is shown to have a large effect on the failure mechanism and stresses.

Figure 1: Schematic of pull-out failure of (45/-45)_s laminate with no fibre fracture

UNNOTCHED TENSILE STRENGTH

A series of tests were carried out on quasi-isotropic IM7/8552 carbon-epoxy laminates with layup $(45_m/90_m/-45_m/0_m)_{ns}$ [3]. With $m=1$, n was varied from 1 to 4, giving laminates from 1 to 4 mm thick with dispersed plies. Keeping $n=1$ and increasing m from 2 to 8 gave laminates from 2 to 8 mm thick with a single set of repeating plies with different ply block thicknesses. The stacking sequence was selected to minimise the risk of edge delamination. Strain energy release rate calculations were performed using a finite element model of a slice perpendicular to the loading direction [4]. This analysis method was applied to all 12 possible symmetric quasi-isotropic stacking sequences with 8 plies, and the one with the highest edge delamination strain of those with a 45° surface ply was selected. The smallest specimens were 1 mm thick, 8 mm wide, with a gauge section of 30 mm, and bonded glass-epoxy end tabs. Thicker specimens had the in-plane dimensions increased in proportion to the thickness so that they were fully scaled.

The expected failure stress was calculated using laminated plate theory with the properties shown in Table 1, and the unidirectional tensile strength of 2806 MPa measured with a small tapered thickness specimen with chamfered plies [3]. This gave a quasi-isotropic strength of 1077 MPa.

Table 1: Ply properties for IM7/8552

0° modulus E_1	161 GPa
90° modulus E_2	11.38 GPa
Shear modulus G_{12}	5.17 GPa
Poisson's ratio ν_{12}	0.32

Experimental results are summarized in Table 2, and plotted in Fig. 2. There are large differences between different layups and none of them reached the expected strength. This is due to initiation of delamination at the free edge. This could clearly be seen in the 2 mm thick specimens with blocked plies, Fig. 3. Subsequently the fibres also break, but the initial failure is controlled by delamination. When more plies are blocked together, delamination occurs at even lower stresses and becomes the main failure mechanism, stepping down through the plies until complete separation occurs at the $-45/0$ interface prior to fibre failure. The same mechanism is believed to control the strength of the dispersed ply specimens, with initiation of free edge delamination leading straight away to fibre failure. In this case the strength actually increases with thickness, because the multiple sublaminates inhibit the free edge delamination initiating from the surface plies.

Laminated plate theory gives the same expected strength for all these cases. The large variation in strengths which are all below this value are due to the differences in delamination behaviour of the different laminates.

Table 2: Unnotched failure stresses of quasi-isotropic IM7/8552 laminates

Blocked plies, m	Repeated sublaminates, n	Thickness (mm)	Lay-up	Failure stress (MPa)
1	4	4	$(45/90/-45/0)_{4S}$	929
1	2	2	$(45/90/-45/0)_{2S}$	911
1	1	1	$(45/90/-45/0)_S$	842
2	1	2	$(45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2)_S$	660
4	1	4	$(45_4/90_4/-45_4/0_4)_S$	458
8	1	8	$(45_8/90_8/-45_8/0_8)_S$	321

Figure 2: Effect of thickness and ply blocking on unnotched tensile strength

Figure 3: Photographs and schematic of failure in $(45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2)_S$ specimens

NOTCHED TENSILE STRENGTH

Delamination and the stress at which it occurs relative to fibre failure is similarly important in notched strength. For example in open hole tension of (45/90/-45/0)s laminates with thick ply blocks delamination and pullout can occur leaving two ligaments of unidirectional material as shown in Fig. 4 [5].

Figure 4: Schematic of pull-out in notched quasi-isotropic laminate

This is shown on a series of scaled specimens of the same material and stacking sequence as the previous unnotched ones. Specimens with a centrally located circular hole were tested in tension with constant width to hole diameter (W/D) and length to hole diameter (L/D) ratios, as shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Open hole specimen geometry

Results of 4 mm thick specimens with blocked plies are plotted in Fig. 6, with a log scale to better cover the wide range of hole sizes from 1.6 to 50.4 mm. All failures were controlled by delamination, and there was a considerable variation in strength with specimen size. There is a clear trend with the strengths transitioning between a lower and a higher asymptote as the hole size increases. Triangular delaminations similar to those observed in the unnotched specimens formed at the intersection of the surface 45° ply and the free edges, and grew gradually across the width between the hole and straight edge in both directions. It appears that the point at which these span the complete width of the specimen corresponds to the point when the delamination is able

to step down through the remaining plies to the -45/0 interface and propagate along the whole length.

Comparing these results with the previous unnotched tests on specimens 32 mm wide with the same layup and similar damage development shows that the unnotched case fits well as an asymptote at large hole sizes, Fig. 6. The size of the triangular delaminations at the free edges is related to the ply block thickness. It might therefore be expected that if the specimen was very narrow, these would be able to join up across the complete width more easily, leading to earlier onset of full delamination. To test this hypothesis, unnotched specimens of the same layup with a width of only 4 mm were tested in tension. These delaminated in a similar way, but at an average stress of only 266 MPa. This is also shown as a line on Fig. 6, and fits well as a lower asymptote.

Figure 6: Effect of hole size on delamination stress of $(45_4/90_4/-45_4/0_4)_s$ laminates

The notched strength of these specimens is therefore controlled by how easily delamination can occur. This depends on two main factors: the absolute ply block thickness, which controls the total amount of energy available to drive delamination and the ratio of ply block thickness to distance from the free edge which affects how easily it can propagate across the width. If the specimens are normalised in such a way as to account for the different propensity to delaminate and plotted against ligament width rather than hole size, we can account for a whole range of different cases on a single plot. This is done using equation (1) to normalise the failure stress by the amount of available energy based on the ply block thickness T_{ply} compared with the baseline 0.5 mm of the specimens shown in Fig. 6.

$$\bar{\sigma} = \sigma \sqrt{T_{ply}/0.5} \quad (1)$$

Results are plotted in Fig. 7 for open hole specimens with thinner and thicker ply blocks, and also for another set of tests on the same material where a W/D ratio of 10 was used as well as 5. All these specimens failed by delamination. A finite width

correction was applied to the latter results to ensure direct comparability. The results all fit reasonably well the trend shown earlier, confirming the parameters controlling tensile strength of open hole specimens failing by delamination.

Figure 7: Effect of ply block thickness and ligament width on delamination of $(45_m/90_m/-45_m/0_m)_s$ laminates

With thinner, dispersed plies this same mechanism causes sub-critical damage development, leading to blunting of the notch before reaching the delamination stress, hence increasing the fibre dominated tensile strength. Open hole tests with the same 4 mm thickness, but with dispersed plies all showed fibre failure, and a decreasing strength with increasing hole size. This is shown in Fig. 8, contrasting with the increasing strength with hole size found for the same thickness specimens with plies blocked together.

Figure 8: Open hole tensile strength of 4 mm thick quasi-isotropic specimens

Although the dispersed ply specimens did not fail by complete delamination, there was still some localised delamination at the hole edge starting at matrix cracks. Initially the size of these delaminations was of the order of the ply thickness, but later they extended and joined up, stepping through the thickness locally. This behaviour adjacent to the hole is similar to that observed globally in the unnotched specimens and in the notched specimens failing by overall delamination. Splitting in the 0° plies also occurred, blunting the notch, and allowing the stress to reach a higher value than the unnotched strength divided by the stress concentration factor.

As the hole size to ply block thickness ratio increases, it becomes more difficult for the delaminations at the hole edge to join up and for splitting to occur, and so this same parameter is also relevant for the fibre failure cases, causing a reduction in strength with increasing size as damage is inhibited. This is illustrated schematically in Fig. 9, showing just the 45° and -45° cracks. For a small hole, the delaminations associated with the transverse cracks almost overlap, facilitating damage linking up through the thickness and propagating.

Figure 9: Delaminations from ply cracks can join up more easily for small holes

The relation between delamination and fibre failure can be better understood by plotting the results controlled by delamination in Fig. 6 and those controlled by fibre failure in Fig. 8 on the same graph, but with the stresses corrected to account for the propensity to delaminate. The normalisation is based on the same principle as equation (1), extended to account for the effect of multiple ply blocks on the amount of energy available to drive delamination of the surface 45 plies where failure initiates. Full details can be found in [5]. Fig. 10 shows that the normalised stresses of the thin dispersed ply specimens are well below the expected delamination stress, explaining why they all fail by fibre fracture.

Tests have also been conducted on 4 mm thick specimens with two repeating sublaminates with 0.25 mm ply blocks, intermediate between the ones with 0.5 mm ply blocks that delaminated, and those with single 0.125 mm plies that gave fibre failures. These are also plotted on Fig. 10. The larger three sizes with 0.25 mm ply blocks all fall well below the trend for delamination, and fibre failures were indeed observed in

these cases. On the other hand the two smallest specimens failed by delamination, consistent with the fit to the blocked ply $m=4, n=1$ data, as discussed before. A transition in failure mode occurs when fibre failure is reached before delamination.

Figure 10: Failure mode and hole size effect for 4 mm ($45_m/90_m/-45_m/0_m$)_{ns} laminates

It is also striking to see the different hole size effects for different ply block thicknesses, which can also be explained in terms of the role of delamination. With thick ply blocks delamination propagates right across the specimen, especially for small hole sizes with narrow ligaments. The delamination becomes the predominant failure mechanism, and gives rise to an increase in strength with hole size when the ratio of W/D is kept constant as it is harder for the delamination to propagate across the wider ligaments.

With thin ply blocks the fibre failure stress is reached well before delamination initiating at the hole edge can propagate across the width, and so fibre failure occurs. It is still more difficult for delamination to propagate as the hole size increases, but this now means that the beneficial effect of delamination and splitting on blunting the notch is reduced. The strength reduces with increasing hole diameter, giving rise to the conventional hole size effect.

With 0.25 mm ply blocks the failure mechanism is at the transition between delamination and fibre failure. In specimens with small holes the delamination propagates across the complete width, constituting failure, whereas for the larger ones fibre failure occurs first. The competing failure mechanisms result in an almost constant strength between 1.6 and 12.7 mm holes.

CONCLUSIONS

Delamination has a major effect on unnotched and notched tensile strength of quasi-isotropic carbon fibre/epoxy laminates. Unnotched specimens with different ply block thicknesses and numbers of sublaminates showed differences in strength of nearly a

factor of three, with failure initiating by delamination at the free edge, and none of the specimens reaching the strength expected from laminated plate theory.

Open hole tension specimens also fail by delamination for thick ply blocks, especially when the ratio of ply thickness to ligament width is large. Specimens with dispersed thin plies fail by fibre fracture before reaching the stress necessary to delaminate across the width. Delamination is still important in controlling splitting, and the associated reduction in the stress concentration factor. Increasing hole size may cause a decrease, increase or neutral effect on tensile strength for different ply block thicknesses depending on the relative propensity to delaminate.

References

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